

ISic0618

Funerary stele of Gnaeus Marcius

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Excavated in December 1922 in the

Coordinates

37.0750458, 15.2590759

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 43118

Physical Description

A rectangular limestone stele with a relief on the upper half of the front face,
and a two line inscription below. The stele is wider at the
base, with a
triangular profile.

Dimensions

Height 58.5 cm
Width 46.2 cm
Depth 12-25.5 cm

Layout

The text is engraved over two lines, on the same field as the relief above, with
a border below.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Wide letters incised in a thin v-cut. Limited use of triangular serifs at the end of
some strokes, and some strokes widen towards the end
(e.g. in the letter R). Letters
of late Republican date. Triangular interpuncts between
words.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60-84 mm
Line 2: 65-78 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cn (aie) · Marci Cn (aii) · f (ilie) · salve

Apparatus

Translation

Gnaeus Marcius, son of Gnaeus, farewell!

Commentary

The inscription has never been formally published, although first reported in the 1929 guide to the museum by Libertini, and subsequently noted by various scholars (see under editions). A parallel for the depiction of a plough on a tombstone has yet to be identified. Manganaro 1962 noted that the plough occurs on coinage, and in some contexts at least serves as a symbol for the foundation of a colonia (see, e.g. E. T. Salmon, *Roman colonization under the Republic* (1969) plate 10, with reference to a Trajanic coin). It seems more likely, in this instance, that the stone provides interesting support for the existence of a distinct, self-identifying category of Roman aratores on the island (in distinction to the commonly attested negotiatores), extensively referenced in Cicero's *In Verrem* orations of 70 BC. A parallel for the vocative+salve in Latin can be seen in a bilingual funerary inscription for a Quintus Domitius from Catania of similar date (ISic0348 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0348>]).

Digital identifiers:

TM 644874

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0618>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4022622

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0618. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338097>

Photo J. Prag